

OSPARK Research Protocol Appendix 3: Discussion Group Notes Template

Thank you for taking part in this group discussion! We really appreciate your time and input. We will be using the notes in this document to conduct qualitative analyses and develop the OSPARK training programme.

Instructions

Please ensure that you have read the participant information sheet and consent form *<add link when available online>*. You may have already completed this at the beginning of the workshop.

This document is for taking notes about your group discussion. **We ask that everyone in the group contributes towards notetaking as a collective effort.** This will ensure that everyone has a chance to contribute, rather than placing the burden of notetaking on one person.

Our research questions are as follows:

- **RQ1:** How do open science advocates engage in outreach activities, and what barriers prevent them from doing so?
- **RQ2:** What training do open science advocates feel they need in marketing, communications, and outreach activities?

Below is a list of questions which you can use to guide your discussion. This is a flexible guideline—if your group talks about something which is relevant to the research questions but is not on the list, this should be explored as much as desired.

If you have any questions or concerns at any point during the discussion, please notify the facilitator(s).

Information

Workshop: *<code for event goes here>*

Group: *<group identifier goes here>*

Number of people in the group: *<add number of participants here>*

Discussion

1. Current marketing, communications, and outreach activities.

In your open science work, how do you currently use...

- social media?
- traditional academic outputs, like conferences or papers?
- other forms of media (e.g. podcasts, videos, blogs, newsletters)?
- marketing and communications techniques, such as communications plans or social media analytics?

If you were asked to conduct marketing and communication activities for the open science initiative(s) you are part of, how would you feel about doing it?

2. Barriers to engaging in marketing, communications, and outreach activities.

What barriers prevent you from engaging in marketing and communication activities for your open science work?

What could your employers do to facilitate your engagement in marketing and communications for your open science initiative?

What barriers might prevent others from engaging in marketing and communication activities?

What do you think could be done to overcome these barriers?

3. Training needs.

What marketing, communications, and outreach training is available to you?

What (if any) training in this area have you completed?

What would you like to see from marketing, communications, and outreach training?

What are your preferred formats for training?

What accessibility barriers have you encountered regarding training or professional development? How could these be overcome?

